

Comparative study of two different species belonging to family xylariaceae

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ABSTRACT

Ascomycetes occupy a wide range of habitats and play a significant role in ecological processes. The Xylariaceae is a family of fungi belonging to the phylum Ascomycota, class Sordariomycetes, and order Xylariales. The family is frequently cited as comprising around 40 to 60 genera. The largest and most well-known genus within this family is *Xylaria*, which contains over 300 to 500+ species (Matik, 2025). The present study focuses on distinguishing between *Xylaria polymorpha* and *Xylaria hypoxylon*, two members of Ascomycetes fungi, in the Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar district of Maharashtra. Field surveys, sample collection, isolation, and regular monitoring were conducted over a six-month period from June 2024 to December 2024. Species identification was performed using standard identification keys and comparative microscopic slide analysis. A total of 32 specimens were collected from different locations across the study area. Among the collected samples, *Xylaria hypoxylon* and *Xylaria polymorpha* were dominant species.

Keywords: Ascomycetes, *Xylaria hypoxylon*, *Xylaria polymorpha*, dead man's finger.

INTRODUCTION

The majority of known fungi belong to the Phylum Ascomycota, which is characterized by the formation of an ascus, a sac-like structure that contains ascospores (Sept.2018). A fruiting body called the ascocarp (S.T. Tilak). The present study examines the biodiversity of *Xylaria* species (Ascomycetes fungi) which belongs from the family Xylariaceae. The fungi of Xylariaceae family are characterized by the formation of stromatic fruiting bodies containing perithecia, which produce asci and ascospores typical of ascomycetous fungi. The family includes several genera such as *Xylaria*, *Hypoxylon*, and *Daldinia*, many of which play an important ecological role in the decomposition of lignocellulosic materials [Osono, T. (2020)]. Species of the genus *Xylaria* are particularly known for their club-shaped stromata and are commonly found growing on dead wood or organic substrates (Stadler,2013). Available literature indicates that studies on Ascomycetes from this region (Chhatrapati Sambhajiagar) are limited. Therefore, systematic documentation and data collection are necessary to better understand

their diversity, and there is also potential for the discovery of previously unreported species. *Xylaria polymorpha* and *Xylaria hypoxylon* were observed as the predominant species in the study area. Variations were recorded between the two species in terms of ascospore characteristics, including size and coloration, as well as differences in the dimensions and morphology of their fruiting bodies. These distinguishing features have been thoroughly examined and documented in the present study.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Collected samples were inoculated on potato dextrose agar media. Growing colonies were observed (Nirmala Ravimannan). Then colonies were compared with natural habitat. The slides were compared with the specimen slides (Fungal Diversity, 2016). Record the place and dates from where and when samples were collected & maintaining the record of the collected material. Photograph of that species own habitat or ecosystem. Naming and labeling the sample is very important to study the diversity of recorded samples (Fungal diversity, 2019).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fungal samples were collected from six different places in Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar: Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad Caves, Sneh Nagar, sai tekdi, sulibhanjan, Himayat baug. Out of total 32 collected samples, 19 samples of ascomycetes were successfully cultured on suitable media. Among these, 9 samples belonged to the genus *Xylaria*, of which two species were found to be dominant, namely *Xylaria hypoxylon* and *Xylaria polymorpha*. The grown colonies were compared with their respective natural habitats. Slides of the collected materials and cultured fungal colonies were

prepared for microscopic examination. Ascomycetes are known to produce sexual spores called ascospores, which are formed inside sac-like structures known as asci (S.T. Tilak). The prepared slides were observed under a microscope and the samples were identified by comparing them with specimen slides (Kirk et al., 2008).

Xylaria hypoxylon was found in the forest and woodland areas of sulibhanjan and Himayat baug, Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar. The genus *Xylaria* belongs to the Kingdom Fungi and is classified under the Division Ascomycota. It falls within the Order Xylariales and the Family Xylariaceae. Thus, *Xylaria* is a member of the Ascomycetous fungi grouped under the family Xylariaceae within the order Xylariales (Barnett, 1990). Morphologically, the specimen exhibited an elongated fruiting body that appeared dark in colour with a whitish tip. It was observed growing on dead wood in a forested area. The collection was carried out during the rainy season under cloudy weather conditions. After culturing on suitable media, 12 colonies were observed. The colonies were whitish in color and resembled those in their natural habitat. Microscopic observation of the prepared slides revealed septate hyphae long tubular filaments divided into cellular segments and eight spores within each ascus (Wessels, 1994).

For laboratory studies, the collected samples were isolated and cultured on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium. Pure cultures were maintained and preserved for further investigation. Microscopic examination was performed by preparing slides and comparing the cultured colonies with their natural habitat characteristics. The stromata are usually dark brown to black in colour and have a rough, carbonaceous surface. This species generally grows on decaying hardwood stumps or buried wood.

Table 1:

Characteristic	<i>Xylaria polymorpha</i>	<i>Xylaria hypoxylon</i>
Common name	Dead Man's Fingers	Candlesnuff Fungus
Fruiting body (stroma) colour	Dark brown to black, thick and club-shaped	Grey to black; young stage often whitish or powdery at the tip
Shape of fruiting body	Thick, finger-like, blunt ends	Slender, branched or antler-like
Spore size	Approximately 20–30 × 6–10 μm	Approximately 12–16 × 4–6 μm
Spore colour	Dark brown to black	Brown to dark brown
Habitat / substrate	Mostly on decaying hardwood stumps and buried wood	On decaying wood, logs, and tree stumps
Surface appearance	Rough, carbonaceous surface	Often covered with white powdery conidia in young stage

Fig 1: **A)** xylaria hypoxylon (frutning body), **B)** fungal colony of xylaria hypoxylon **C)** Ascospores **D)** Asci, **E)** xylaria polymorpha **F)** fungal colony of xylaria polymorpha, **G)** T.S. of xylaria polymorpha, **H)** Asci.

The ascospores of *Xylaria polymorpha* are comparatively larger, measuring approximately $20\text{--}30 \times 6\text{--}10 \mu\text{m}$, and they are dark brown to black in colour. *Xylaria polymorpha* was found in Snehanagar and Van Vibhag areas of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar. A total of 21 colonies were observed on media. Each colony appeared white in color, though slightly different from its natural habitat. Microscopic examination revealed a large number of ascospores within asci, and the observed ascospores were similar to those found in the natural habitat.

The genus *Xylaria* is taxonomically classified under the Kingdom Fungi and belongs to the Division Ascomycota. It is placed within the Order Xylariales and the Family Xylariaceae. Therefore, *Xylaria* represents a genus of ascomycetous fungi categorized under the family Xylariaceae in the order Xylariales. The *Xylaria* specimen was collected from Snehanagar, Van Vibhag Kokanwadi, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar. This genus is commonly encountered in forested regions, particularly on decaying or damaged wood, often near moist environments such as ponds or water bodies. Previous studies have also reported its association with decomposing wood in humid habitats (Hyde, 2018). The frutning bodies are slender and

often branched, resembling small antlers or candle snuff, which is why it is commonly called the "Candlesnuff fungus." The stromata are grey to black in colour and frequently show a whitish powdery coating at the tips during the early stage due to the presence of conidia. The ascospores of *Xylaria hypoxylon* are smaller than those of *Xylaria polymorpha*, measuring about $12\text{--}16 \times 4\text{--}6 \mu\text{m}$, and are typically brown to dark brown in colour.

CONCLUSION

The comparative study of *Xylaria polymorpha* and *Xylaria hypoxylon*, two species belonging to the genus *Xylaria* of the family Xylariaceae, highlights significant morphological differences between them. Both species are wood-decaying fungi commonly found on dead or decaying wood and play an important ecological role in the decomposition process. However, they differ in characteristics such as the shape and colour of the frutning bodies as well as the size of their spores. *Xylaria polymorpha* is characterized by thick, dark, finger-like stromata and comparatively larger spores, whereas *Xylaria hypoxylon* shows slender, branched stromata with smaller spores and often a whitish powdery tip during early development. These

distinguishing features are important for accurate identification and classification of species within the Xylariaceae family

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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